

**INFLUENCE OF HOME ENVIRONMENT THROUGH
PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT ON PUPILS' ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS
IN AINABKOI SUB-COUNTY KENYA**

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Abstract:

Are poor results in Kenyan public schools a result of lack of parental support and poor learning environment at home? What impact would parental involvement in their children's schoolwork have on their academic performance? These are the key questions that this paper seeks to address. Focusing on public primary schools in Ainabkoi Sub County, Kenya, the authors sought to determine the influence of home environment through parental involvement on the academic performance of their children. The study was guided by Joyce Epstein's framework of six types of parental involvement and adopted ex-post facto research design. The target population comprised 2404 Class 8 pupils and 61 class teachers in public primary schools in Ainabkoi Sub County. Stratified and simple random sampling methods were used to select 331 class eight pupils who participated in the study. Census approach was employed in which all the class teachers were involved in the study. Questionnaire and interview schedule were used as data collection instruments. Validity of the instruments was ensured through a pilot study while test-retest technique was employed to check the reliability of the questionnaire. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

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Descriptive statistics were analyzed in form of percentages, frequencies and means, and then presented using pie charts and tables. Chi-square was used to test the hypotheses of the study which established that there was a positive and significant relationship between home environment as indicated by ($\chi^2=7.325$; $p=.001$) and pupils' academic performance in Ainakboi sub County. The study concluded that home environment had a statistically significant influence on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools. The study recommends that parents should provide their children with the required learning materials at home such as basic needs to create a conducive home environment that will improve their academic performance.

Keywords: parental involvement, home environment, academic performance, public primary schools, Ainabkoi sub-county

1. Introduction

Parental involvement is the awareness and active participation of parents in their children's education. It involves an understanding of the interaction between parenting skills and pupil success in schooling and a commitment to consistent communication with teachers about pupils' progress. Parental involvement takes different forms ranging from providing the children with conducive environment for learning at home to engaging in educational activities both at home and in school. Academic performance generally refers to how well a student is accomplishing his or her tasks and studies and is measured by their grade (scores) at the national examination level.

Mainly, family has a responsibility to socialize the children for making them productive members of society. According to Muriithi (2015), the more parents were involved in the process of imparting education to their children, the more the children excelled in their academic career. They also translated to productive and responsible members of society. According to the Children Act (2001), children have a right to education which needs the support of parents. The best interest of the child must be presented at all times and in all actions and decisions that affect them. This was also stipulated in the Education Act, (2012) which stressed the importance of schools partnering with parents to ensure a quality education and nurturing environment for children.

In USA, evidence of parental involvement in education existed both at home and within the school. The No Child Left behind Act of 2001 recognized parental involvement and empowerment in determining the quality of teaching and learning processes in schools (Education Department, 2004). Parents were important in providing environmental, social and economic factors, which had powerful effects on pupils' academics. Ciriaka (2013) observed that parent's willingness to contact teachers about their children's progress was perhaps the first step to becoming involved in education.

In UK, Goldberg and Zwiebel (2011) revealed that there was a sweeping plunge in student's academic performance in national examination compared to performance in similar examination in Far East countries like Singapore and China. The education experts attributed the poor performance to lack of parental involvement in educational activities. Other countries in Europe showed an improvement in results raising the question as to why the difference was being experienced.

In California, Becker, Nakagawa and Corwin (2011) asserted that parents' academic interaction propelled the ways students performed in secondary schools. Parents instilled skills, behaviors and attitudes in students that greatly improved their academic performance. Parental involvement therefore increased educational effectiveness of their children being affirmed by 71% of the Principals and 59% of the teachers. The current study thus compares the results in California a developed country with Kenya's situation as a developing country. Research undertaken had led to a paradigm shift from exclusive professionalism and opened up discussion on the importance of parental involvement. Bridgemohan (2012) asserted that parents had a right to play an active role in their children's education while according to Symeou (2003) parents at all levels were concerned about their children's education and success and wanted advice and help from schools on ways of helping their children. Brannon (2012) also noted that parental involvement led to higher academic achievement and improved the perception of children's competence. Other researches associated parental involvement with the improvement of grades, GPA, attendance, and decrease in negative behavior Correlating parental involvement to student success in academic achievement (Banerjee, Zage, Harrell, & Johnson, 2011; Malone, 2015; McNeal, 2014).

Parental involvement contributed to youth academic success (Houtenville & Conway, 2008). Children were more likely to apply themselves and perform better in school when their parents showed interest in their schoolwork, were willing to assist them with homework and hold their children accountable for non-completion of school assignment. Children who were not working hard at school however began to perceive school as valuable when their parents actively exhibited that they valued school through their involvement (Teklemariam & Akala, 2011). An evaluation of parental involvement in primary schools identified parental involvement to be a significant contributor to the mental capacity, social and cognitive behavior of students (Hornby & White, 2010; Nitecki, 2015). According to Smith, Wohlstetter, Kuzi and De Pedro (2011), parental involvement increased the likelihood that students came to school more prepared. According to Cheung and Pomerantz (2015), parents who participated in school and home activities increased learning outcomes of their children. Ultimately, parents who assisted students with their homework not only contributed to their preparedness but also ability to articulate prior knowledge and grasp new concepts.

Kenya's 2017 KCPE results for primary schools indicated deterioration in average mean score particularly in Ainabkoi Sub County with only few students transforming to secondary schools. The Sub-County Education Officer (AEO, 2014), lamented that most public primary schools despite having the required instruments for

curriculum instruction they performed poorly in national examinations. Formation of a joint committee of education officers and head-teachers (Chemagosi, 2012), saw the team come up with a list of factors contributing to poor performance among them unfavorable home environments. In this they cited lack of concern by parents in the involvement of their children's education resulting to a minimal impact on nurturing pupils towards academic achievement. The role of parental involvement in enhancing academic performance has been largely unrecognized in Kenya placing a lot of emphasis on use of continuous assessment tests, teacher training and administrative restructuring (Republic of Kenya, 2007). It is against this background that this study investigated the influence of home environment through parental involvement on pupils' academic performance in Ainabkoi Sub County.

2. Joyce Epstein's Framework of Parental Involvement

An effective form of involvement was presented by Epstein's model (2002) which described how children learn and develop through three overlapping "spheres of influence." These were: Family, school and the community. These three spheres form partnership to best meet the needs of the child. Epstein defines six types of involvement based on the relationship between family, school and the community: Parenting skills, communication, volunteering, learning at home, and decision making and collaborating with the community. Epstein (2002) emphasized that all of these six types of involvement must be included to have successful partnership. Pupils who have support from the parents at home show better performance at school, while students lacking support were struggling (Epstein, 2002).

The first type covers the basic needs of children by having parents involved in routine activities such as preparing their child for school (Smith et al. 2011).

Epstein's second type includes all forms of communication between the school and parents (Epstein's, 1987; El Nokali et al., 2010).

Type 3 Epstein's model involves parents being involved in the activities of the school by performing volunteer duties on behalf of their child (Epstein, 1987).

The fourth type of parent involvement consists of home activities related to school (Epstein, 1987).

In a study by Altschul (2011), the effect of parental involvement were analyzed and found to be more effective using home activities rather than active school involvement. Altschul, reported Latino parents felt that school environment were uninviting and therefore, it was easier for parents to help their children at home rather than feel unwanted at their child's school. The fifth type of parental involvement represents parental participation in parents association, school boards, and committees while in the sixth type, parents connect to community organizations and utilize community resources (Smith et al., 2011).

3. Literature Review

The academic performance of any student cannot be separated from the home environment in which the pupil lives. Healthy home environment offers emotional security to a child. Education has one of its basic tasks as to train young people to become useful members of the society. This training begins at home in the informal way. The home of the child is the first place he enters as is born into the world by his or her parents. In Namibia, Guolaun (2010) conducted a qualitative survey study on the extent of parental involvement in students' academic performance. The study involved seven parents of students who had achieved high grades in examinations. All parents reported very high level of involvement in their children's education, but the study was limited in design since the sample was too small to make generalization to a larger population.

Nyarko (2011) investigated the effect of parental involvement in school on students' academic performance in Ghana. The study employed survey research design. The target population was 310 parents and students in Ghana secondary schools. The results revealed a positive and significant correlation between mothers' school involvement and academic performance of children. The study also established that there was non-significant correlation between fathers' school involvement and students' academic performance. The study however found a positive and a significant correlation between mothers and fathers; home involvement and the academic achievement of the adolescents. Mdada (2000), who conducted a study to examine the impact of home-environment on pupils' academic achievement, found that children whose fathers involved themselves in their school matters fared reasonably well in terms of academic performance than those pupils whose fathers did not get involved.

Osei-Akodo, Chowa and Ansong (2012) investigated the extent of parental involvement in academic performance in Ghana using randomized cluster sampling of 100 schools from eight out of ten regions. The results indicated that majority of the parents (83%) hardly assisted children in their homework. The study did not however establish the effect of parental involvement on academic performance. In Kenya, Kibet (2010) investigated the role of parents in enhancing primary school children's education in Uasin-Gishu County, Kenya and found that parental involvement in education was low. This study was however limited in scope covering only pre-primary schools. Ciaraka (2003) did a research that sought to establish the role of parents in facilitating the learning processes in selected primary schools in Egoji-Meru and found that parental involvement in homework was high but majority (93%) of the parents did not check their children's exercise books regularly. Sporns (2011) also indicated no shared responsibility between parents and schools in Kenyan rural primary schools and that schools were solely responsible for students' education and there was hardly any relationship between parental involvement and students' academic performance. This study was limited in design and scope given that it covered only one school involving a

sample of twelve respondents. This sample was too small to get sufficient data to allow generalizations to the entire population.

Otewa, Role and Makena (2011) on the other hand explored parental factors affecting academic performance of Standard six pupils in Kisumu city – Kenya. Their study found that parental involvement had a significant positive correlation with students' academic achievement ($r=0.247$, $p=000$). Parental involvement accounted for 24.7% variation in students' academic performance. A study conducted by Koskei (2014) on influence of parental involvement on students' academic performance in Kuresoi Sub-County indicated that the level of parental involvement appeared to have no direct influence on students' performance in mixed day schools. He cited one reason as being pressure exerted on students by parents to get high marks without taking into consideration the abilities of their children. The nature of encouragement given to the child by his/her parents is important. Parents who pressurize their children by making high demands may create in them anxiety and fear for the failure instead of providing effective motivation to do well in their academic work.

A recent quasi-experimental education intervention study done by Abuya, Ngware, Hungi and Oketch (2014) involving over 1,200 girls living in two Nairobi Urban slums in Kenya, in this intervention study girls were exposed to various education intervention including parental involvement. Evidence from this study revealed that girls who enjoyed parental involvement in their schooling significantly improved their education aspiration by 13 standardized mean score than those not exposed to parental involvement package intervention. Similarly, the same girls significantly increased their numeracy and literacy than those not exposed to parental involvement intervention package. From this research, there is evidence that parental involvement in pupils learning goes a long way in shaping and molding the pupils' education outcome.

A research study was conducted by Fantuzzo and Power (2004) in Stephanie Children's School in the District of Philadelphia. The study focused on multiple dimensions of family involvement and their relations to behavior and learning competences. The study comprised 144 school children aged between 46 to 68 months (3-5 years) from urban settings. About 46% of the children in the study were African America males. Parent participants in the study ranged between 18 and 74 years, 73% of who were mothers, 8% were fathers, 9% were grandparents and 10% were other relatives or foster parents. The study used questionnaires and correlation analysis. The parents were of different levels of education from high school to university level. According to the study findings, it was found that home-based involvement was related to pro social, peer play interactions both at home and at school. It also indicated that parental involvement programs focus on improving the home learning environment through parent education, provision of learning materials increased children motivation and self-efficacy. The school based parental involvement was associated with lower levels of disruptive peer play across the two contexts. Results from the home school conferencing were not found to be related to peer play behavior

in either the home or the school setting. However, the overall study demonstrated that parental involvement dimensions were associated with different learning and classroom behavioral adjustment outcomes. For example, home-based parental involvement activities such as reading to a child at home, providing a place for educational activities and asking a child about school, evidenced the strongest relationships to later pre-school classroom competences. The activities were related to children's approaches to learning, motivation, attention, persistence and to positive receptive vocabulary. The study also identified that home-based involvement was associated with significantly lower levels of classroom behavior problems.

The importance of the child's home environment and his / her learning at home is also emphasized by the ACSSO (2006) which observes that families have the biggest influence on the child's development, and that learning language and social discourse occur at home in non-formal by talking across the breakfast table, chatting on a bus ride or reading a bedtime story during the first years and it actually continues virtually all the time, even as the child gets older and demand to be independent. Children are motivated to work on activities and learn new information and skills when their environments are rich in interesting activities that arouse their curiosity and offer moderate challenges. Unfortunately, there is much variability in motivational influences in homes. Some homes have many activities that stimulate children thinking such as computer, books, puzzles and parents who may be heavily interested in their children's cognitive development and spent time with them on learning. Much of the variability in the relation between family income and children's intellectual development comes from the parents' provision of stimulating home (Yeung, Linver & Brooks, 2002). Children intellectual development is most strongly influenced by the home environment during infancy and early childhood. There is much evidence supporting the hypothesis that the quality of a child's early learning in the home environment relate positively to the development of intelligent and reading skills and parental involvement in schooling also predict achievement (Luckner, Whaley & Egeland, 2004).

Muindi (2010) reported that the Kenya National Examinations Council carried out a survey to find out what determines the performance of students at the end of the school cycle. The survey also examined the children's personal, home and school profiles and how they support and hinder learning. A total of 7931 pupils were interviewed in 328 primary schools in 76 districts countrywide. The study indicated that only 17% of fathers and 36% of mothers in Nairobi helped their children with homework. According to the study, the job of helping children with homework was left to siblings (46%). The study also showed that more than 60% of parents were not taking a close interest in their children's homework. Eighty-eight per cent of the pupils interviewed admitted that they were given homework at school, yet only half reported having been helped by their parents. The fathers were found not to be taking interest in their children's homework. The survey also indicated that only 17% of fathers helped their children in doing their homework.

4. Material and Methods

The study adopted ex post facto design since home environment through parental involvement could not be directly manipulated. This design is supported by Nachmias and Nachmias (1996) stating that it is useful when trying to describe patterns of relationships between variables that cannot be manipulated, hence parental involvement in their children's education. According to the data obtained from the County Education Office as per October 2018 there are 61 public primary schools in the sub-county. The study therefore targeted 2404 Class 8 pupils and 61 class teachers.

The sample size of the pupils was obtained using Krejcie and Morgan (1970). The study employed stratified sampling and simple random sampling techniques to select a sample of 331 pupils. The students were stratified based on their gender from which simple random sampling technique was used to obtain the sample size. Census approach was also employed in which all the 61 class teachers were involved in the study.

The study employed questionnaires (Kombo & Tromp, 2006) and structured interview schedule (David & Sutton, 2004) for collection of data. The content validity of the questionnaire was sought through expert consultation with professionals in the education sector. Their suggestions and comments were used as a basis to modify the question items and make them adaptable to the study. After a pilot study, construct validity was determined by using factor analysis then compared with the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of 0.5 (Kothari, 2004). Face to face validity was also determined by the authors.

Both questionnaire and interview schedule were piloted in a primary school in the locality similar to the study area but not involved in the study. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) normally the pilot sample should be between 1% and 10% of the larger sample. Data collected from the pilot study was used to rephrase and recognize the instrument so as to enhance their validity and reliability. Test-retest technique of assessing reliability of a research instrument was also employed to guarantee that the information initially given would be reliable (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2008). According to Kothari (2004), data analysis is the process of bringing order and meaning to raw data. Both quantitative and qualitative methods of analyses were used. Descriptive analysis was conducted as well as inferential statistics that involved Chi square tests.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Demographic Data of Pupils

The pupils were asked to indicate their demographic information based on their gender category and performance. Gender responses are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Gender of Pupils

Results show that (42.7%) of the pupils were male while (57.3%) were female. This ensured equality and balanced responses on their perception on the influence of home environment on their academic achievement.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Pupils

Ages of Teachers	Frequency	Percentage
10-12 years	31	9.4%
13-15 years	193	58.6%
16-18 years	106	32.0%
Total	330	100%

The study also sought to ascertain the age distribution of pupils in Ainabkoi Sub County. To achieve this objective, the respondents were asked to indicate their ages using the age brackets provided. Their responses were as summarized in Table 1. This indicates that (58.6%) of the pupils were aged 13-15 years while 32.0% were aged 16-18 years. The youngest cohort of pupils was aged 10-12 years. Therefore, majority of the pupils in public primary schools in Ainabkoi Sub County were aged from 13-15 years which is the appropriate year of the pupils to complete class eight.

Figure 2: Caregivers of the Pupils

The study also sought to investigate the pupils' caregivers. The findings indicated that majority 76.9% of the pupils had both mother and father as caregivers,

12.6% had single mothers, 1.9% had a single father and 8.6% were raised by guardians. The findings implied that majority of the pupils had both parents who were contributing towards their education.

Table 2: Parents' Level of Education

Highest Level of Education of parents	Frequency	Percentage
Post-Secondary	95	28.9%
Secondary	198	60.0%
Primary	20	5.9%
Below class eight	16	4.6%
Total	330	100%

Results show that (28.9%) of parents had attained a post-secondary level of education, 60.0% of the parents had secondary level of education, while 5.9% and 4.6% of the parents had a primary and below class eight level of education respectively. The findings implied that majority of the parents were knowledgeable enough to assist their children in primary school educational activities such as homework and also understood the importance of education on their children. Moreover, the pupils were asked to indicate the marks they scored in the previous end term examinations. The mean and standard deviation were calculated, and results are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Performance of Pupils in Examinations

	n	Min score	Max score	Mean	Std. Deviation
End term examinations marks	330	210.00	389.00	277.41	30.59

It was found out that the maximum mark achieved was 389 while the least was 210 marks with a mean of 277.41 and a standard deviation of 30.59. This performance was considered average because the mean was just past half mark which is usually 250 of the total 500 marks. The findings implied that majority of the students attained an average grade in the examinations.

5.2 Influence of Home Environment on Pupils' Academic Performance

The study sought to determine the influence of home environment on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools. This objective was obtained through formulation of a set of eight statements anchored on a five-point Likert scale whose findings are depicted in Table 4.

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Table 4: Influence of Home Environment on Pupils' Academic Performance

Pupils' perception	N	Min	Max	Mean	S. Dev
My parent/guardian always ensure there is controlled peer association while at home	330	1.00	5.00	3.94	1.25
My parent/guardian set study rules at home to children	330	1.00	5.00	3.77	1.36
My parent/guardian has set a study room at home for me	330	1.00	5.00	2.51	1.24
My parent/guardian control when and what I watch television	330	1.00	5.00	3.56	1.38
My parent/guardian supervise learning at home	330	1.00	5.00	3.23	1.42
My parent/guardian calls child on phone when they are away	330	1.00	5.00	3.20	1.23
I am praised by my parent/guardian when I perform well in school	330	1.00	5.00	3.17	1.40
I am disciplined by my parent/guardian whenever I make mistakes at home	330	1.00	5.00	2.91	1.37
Valid N (Listwise)	330	1	5	3.44	1.33

Source: Field Data, 2018.

The pupils were asked to indicate their opinions on the influence of home environment through involvement of parents on their academic performance. The study asked them to indicate on the provided scale how they agreed with statements on the matter. The results of the pupils' perceptions as displayed in Table 4 show that majority of pupils agreed (M=3.94 and SD=1.25) with the statement that parent/guardian always ensured there was controlled peer association while at home. As to whether parents set study rules at home to children the pupils also agreed (M=3.76 and SD=1.35) with the statement. This shows that parents at home were keen on what their children learnt, and they monitored how their children learnt.

A class teacher in one of the schools said:

"Though some of the pupils are assisted by their parents on their homework, majority of the pupils seem not assisted at all. Lack of necessary knowledge due to high level of illiteracy among the parents could be attributed to the reasons why the parents do not assist their children in homework."

When asked whether their parent/guardian had provided a study room at home, the findings indicated that majority of the pupils tended to disagree (M=2.51 and SD=1.24) with the statement. This implied that in majority of the homes in Ainabkoi Sub County there were no study rooms for the children. When asked as to whether parents controlled when and what they watch on television, a significant portion of the pupils as indicated by (M=3.56 and SD=1.37) supported the statement.

A teacher supported the finding from the pupils and said that:

"Most of the students in the schools came to school without the necessary learning materials such as pens, writing materials, clean uniform and some of the pupils even go without lunch. This is attributed to the fact that some of the children are living in abject poverty and cannot afford learning materials."

The findings were consistent with Fantuzzo and Power (2004) in Stephanie Children's School in the District of Philadelphia which established that parental involvement in home-based activities such as home learning environment through parent education, provision of learning materials increased children motivation and self-efficacy which were associated with improved learning and classroom behavioral adjustment outcomes. The study highlighted that home-based parental involvement activities such as reading to a child at home, providing a place for educational activities and asking a child about school, evidenced the strongest relationships to later pre-school classroom competences.

When asked whether their parent/guardian supervised their learning at home, majority of the pupils were in agreement ($M=3.23$ and $SD=1.42$). The findings supported Ciaraka's (2003) study on the role of parents in facilitating the learning processes in selected primary schools in Egoji- Meru which established that parental involvement in homework was high. The findings however contradicted Osei-Akodo, Chowa and Ansong (2012) in a study on the extent to which parental involvement influence academic performance of pupils in Ghana which established that majority of the parents (83%) hardly assisted children in homework. The findings also contradicted Kibet's (2010) study on the role of parents in enhancing primary school children's education in Uasin-Gishu district, Kenya and found that parental involvement in education was low.

On whether the parent/guardian called child on phone when they were away ($M=3.20$ and $SD=1.23$). The study also sought to investigate whether the pupils were praised by their parent/guardian when they performed well in school. The findings of $M=3.17$ and $SD=1.40$ implied that majority of the pupils were praised by their parents when they performed well in their education. On whether the pupils were disciplined by their parent/guardian whenever they made mistakes at home, majority of the pupils agreed ($M=2.91$ and $SD=1.37$). In general, the pupils had a positive perception ($M=3.43$ and $SD=1.32$) on the influence of home environment on their academic performance in Ainabkoi sub county. Although, some pupils believed that home environment was not a significant predictor of their academic performance as evidenced by standard deviation scores of 1.32 which was high, the findings showed that home environment was a contributor to the pupils' academic performance in Ainabkoi Sub County, Kenya. The findings implied that when the pupils are provided with a conducive environment at home to learn they performed better as compared to pupils whom the home environment was unconducive and poor for learning. To evaluate the influence of home environment and pupil's academic performance, a chi-square test was conducted. To check if there existed significant difference, a chi square was computed at 95% confidence level and the results are presented in Table 5.

5.3 Decision Rule

If p- value is less than or equal to 0.05 reject the Null hypothesis. If p- value is greater than 0.05 do not reject the Null hypothesis.

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Table 5: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.325 ^a	4	.001
Likelihood Ratio	8.090	4	.132
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.126	1	.140
N of Valid Cases	330		

The null hypothesis tested was that home environment had no significant relationship on pupils' academic performance. The results show that the values are $\chi^2=7.325$, $df=4$ and $p=.001$ (Table 5) which was less than the level of significance 0.05 thus the null hypothesis was rejected. The findings implied that there exists a significant relationship ($p<0.05$) between home environment and pupil's academic performance in primary schools in Ainabkoi sub county. This implied that provision of conducive home environment in which the pupils were provided with study rooms, were disciplined when they made mistakes and also providing all the necessary support at home to the pupils had an influence on their academic performance. The findings were a clear indication that the academic performance of any student could not be separated from the home environment in which the pupil lives. Healthy home environment offers emotional security to a child. Education has one of its basic tasks as to train young people to become useful members of the society. This training begins at home in the informal way. The home of the child is the first place he enters as is born into the world by his or her parents. The findings supported Nyarko's (2011) study on the effect of parental involvement in school on students' academic performance in Ghana. The results showed a positive and significant correlation between mothers' school involvement and academic performance of children. The study found a positive and a significant correlation between mothers' and fathers' home involvement and the academic achievement of the adolescents.

The findings were also consistent with Mdada (2000), the study that examined the impact of home-environment on pupils' academic achievement and found that children's whose fathers involved themselves in school matters fared reasonably well in terms of academic performance than those pupils whose fathers did not get involved. Sporns (2011) indicated no shared responsibility between parents and schools in Kenyan rural primary schools and that schools were solely responsible for students' education and there was hardly any relationship between parental involvement and students' academic performance. The findings also supported Otewa, Role and Makena (2011) exploration on parental factors affecting academic performance of grade six pupils in Kisumu city, Kenya which found that parental involvement had a significant positive correlation with students' academic achievement ($r=0.247$, $p=000$).

The findings were also in tandem with Pomerantz, Wang, Qian, and Florrie (2005) study on mothers' effect in the context of children's homework in Washington. The study established that mothers' involvement in their children's homework improved their performance. The study highlighted that parental participation in the educational activities enhanced parent-child relationship, child behavior and

motivation and other psychological patterns of the learner. The findings were also in tandem with De Planly, Coulter Kern, and Duchane (2007) study which indicated that parental involvement at home was more important for academic achievement than involvement at the school. The study highlighted that only parental involvement at home had a positive effect on achievement and adjustment.

Inconsistencies were however recorded with Koskei's (2014) study on the influence of parental involvement on students' academic performance in Kuresoi Sub-County which revealed that the level of parental involvement appeared to have no direct influence on students' performance in mixed day schools. The study cited that parental pressure exerted on students to get high marks without taking into consideration the abilities of their children had a negative effect of the children academic performance.

The findings also contradicted Muindi's (2010) findings which indicated that only 17% of fathers and 36% of mothers in Nairobi helped their children with homework. According to the study, the job of helping children with homework was left to siblings (46%). The study also showed that more than 60% of parents were not taking a close interest in their children's homework. Eighty-eight per cent of the pupils interviewed admitted that they were given homework at school, yet only half reported having been helped by their parents. The fathers were found not to be taking interest in their children's homework. The survey indicated that only 17% of fathers helped their children in doing their homework.

6. Recommendations

The study recommended that parents should work hard to provide conducive home environment to promoted pupils' academic performance. The study recommended that parents should provide studying materials for their children should assist them in their homework and provide all the necessary support at home to the pupils.

7. Conclusion

The study concluded that the home environment had a statistically significant relationship with pupils' academic performance. That provision of conducive home environment in which the pupils were provided with study rooms, were disciplined when they made mistakes and also providing all the necessary support at home to the pupils had a positive influence on their academic performance.

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